

Cycle Slip Correction and Coherency Detection for Precision Altimetry Using Dual-Frequency GG-R Measurements

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Global Navigation Satellite System Reflectometry (GNSS-R) is an emerging remote sensing technique with different applications in environmental monitoring, such as soil moisture and surface water mapping. A specialized variant, Grazing Angle GNSS-R (GG-R), uses GNSS dual-frequency reflected and direct signals between GNSS transmitters, specular points, and low Earth orbit (LEO) receivers for precision altimetry. A critical step in the GG-R data processing workflow involves unwrapping the phase measurements and correcting for cycle slips. If left uncorrected, cycle slips introduce significant uncertainties in height retrieval.

In this study, GG-R measurements are collected by Spire Global Inc. grazing angle constellation, originally designed for radio occultation and later reprogrammed to collect reflected signals under grazing angle geometries [1]. Dual-frequency L1 and L2 phase information over Hudson Bay are processed for a 3-month period from July 1 to September 30, 2021. Height retrievals are performed using a Kalman Filter-based phase unwrapping approach called Adaptive-SCANF(ASCANF), which incorporates a coherency detection algorithm. The ASCANF introduces modifications in the computation of variances, distinguishing it from the simultaneous cycle-slip and noise

filtering (SCANF) approach. The SCANF algorithm processes GG-R dual-frequency L1 and L2 phase observations as follows [2]:

$$\mathbf{y}[k] = [\Phi_{L1}[k] \ \Phi_{L2}[k]]^T \quad (1)$$

The state vector \mathbf{x} consists of the filtered L1 and L2 phase residuals and their non-dispersive rates:

$$\mathbf{x}[k] = [\Phi_{L1}[k] \ \Phi_{L2}[k] \ \nabla\Phi_S[k] \ \nabla\Phi_I[k]]^T \quad (2)$$

Phase residuals are modeled as:

$$\mathbf{y}[k] = [\mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}[k] + \mathbf{B}[k] + \mathbf{v}[k]]^T \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{B} represents an estimate of biases due to cycle slips, and measurement the noise is modeled as $\mathbf{v}[k] \sim N(0, R[k])$:

$$\mathbf{R}[k] = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{L1}^2[k] & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{L2}^2[k] \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The variances for L1 and L2 in ASCANF are estimated during post-processing with the phase residuals \mathbf{y} (raw measurements). They are computed over a sliding window, with the window size determined based on the value of T .

A coherency detection algorithm is implemented using circular length (ζ) and circular kurtosis (K) with a maximum tolerable segment size of 3 seconds [3]:

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{N} \left| \sum_{i=1}^N \cos a_i + \sum_{i=1}^N \sin a_i \right| \quad (5)$$

$$K = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cos(2(a_i - \bar{a}_i))$$

K and ζ are computed for each segment of each phase. These values are analyzed using k-means clustering ($k = 3$), which categorize the GG-R data into coherent, semi-coherent, and incoherent classes. The classification criteria for the coherency detection algorithm are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Coherent: } & \zeta > 0.8 \text{ and } K > 0.235 \\ \text{Semi-coherent: } & \zeta > 0.46 \text{ and } K > -0.0135 \\ \text{Incoherent: } & \zeta \leq 0.46 \text{ and } K \leq -0.0135 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In this study, phase coherency analysis is applied to both L1 and L2 phases. For a segment to be classified as coherent, both circular kurtosis and circular length calculated over the segment size, must satisfy the coherence criterion in Eq. 6.

Figure 1 illustrates L1 and L2 phases from a track example over Hudson Bay on July 2, 2021, at 02:27:30. The left panel shows the uncorrected phases, while the central panel displays the corrected replicas estimated using the ASCANF algorithm. The right panel represents the corrected replicas derived from a geometry-free approach [4].

Figure 1. Uncorrected L1 and L2 phases from a track example over Hudson Bay on July 2, 2021, at 02:27:30 AM (left panel), corrected phase residuals using ASCANF (central panel), and geometry-free combination (right panel). Segments are color-coded based on their coherence status.

The GG-R height retrieval incorporates several parameters, including the relative geometric delay, geometric differences derived from phase and atmospheric delays, the reference surface, and the elevation angle. Ionospheric delay correction is based on the frequency-specific approach [4], while phase measurements are corrected for tropospheric delay using NCEP Global Forecast System (GFS) analysis model. Surface height deviations are adjusted to the DTU18 reference surface, corrected for ocean tides using TPXO9-atlas.

Height retrievals based on ASCANF, a single frequency approach with coherence identification using circular length and circular kurtosis, are compared with relative heights derived from a geometry-free combination of phase residuals. The latter method applies cycle slip corrections to the unwrapped phase residuals and a moving window over the phase derivatives for coherency detection [5]. Figure 2 (left panel) depicts the RMS error histogram for 670 GG-R tracks, demonstrating that the ASCANF algorithm, combined with circular kurtosis and circular length, achieve better RMS differences compared to the geometry-free approach. Figure 2 (right panel) illustrates RMS differences of all GG-R tracks over Hudson Bay during a 3-month period from July 1, 2021, to September 30, 2021. Lower RMS values are observed in the northeastern region (dark blue), while some outliers represented in turquoise and yellow, suggest opportunities for further algorithm improvement.

The method ASCANF incorporating circular kurtosis and circular length, demonstrates potential for improving precision altimetry in GNSS-R. Unlike the geometry-free approach, ASCANF relies less on the interaction between L1 and L2 phases and it is more robust against noise. The adaptability of the ASCANF lies in its potential for future modifications, particularly in adjusting or reweighting phase segments based on coherence as needed.

Figure 2. Distribution of RMS differences of 670 GG-R tracks (left panel), with green representing the results based on ASCANF and blue representing results derived from the geometry-free combination of phase residuals. The right panel shows the geophysical coverage of RMS differences of the 670 GG-R tracks over Hudson Bay.

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